

Supplementary Information: Methods S1

Sampling, genome size, chromosome counting and ploidy level estimations of *Brachypodium*

Individual plants from ten vouchered *Brachypodium* species and ecotypes [diploids *B. arbuscula*, *B. pinnatum* and *B. stacei*, and polyploids *B. boissieri*, *B. hybridum*, *B. mexicanum*, *B. phoenicoides* (Bpho6 and Bpho422 accessions), *B. retusum* and *B. rupestre*] collected in their native circum-Mediterranean, Eurasian and North American (Mexico) regions were studied. Additional data from vouchered diploids *B. distachyon* and *B. sylvaticum* was incorporated to the study. Our sampling covered all the recognized diploid species that represent the main evolutionary splits of the genus (Catalán *et al.*, 2016; Díaz-Pérez *et al.*, 2018) (Table S2).

Leaves of vouchered adult plants growing in pots were used for genome size (GS) estimation through flow cytometry. Nuclear suspensions were prepared from 200 mg of leaf sample and leaf internal standard. The nuclear DNA content of *B. retusum* was calculated using nuclei isolated from young leaves of *Raphanus sativus* “Saxa” (1.11 pg/2C DNA; Doležel *et al.*, 2007) and those of *B. arbuscula*, *B. boissieri*, *B. mexicanum*, *B. phoenicoides*, *B. pinnatum* and *B. rupestre* using *Lycopersicon esculentum* ‘Stupicke’ (1.96 pg/2C DNA; Doležel *et al.*, 2007) as standards. Nuclei were stained with propidium iodide and samples were analyzed using a CyFlow Ploidy Analyser SYSMEX following the protocol of Doležel *et al.* (2007). At least 5,000 nuclei were analyzed per sample. Each sample (two replicates) was analyzed three times on different days. Only measurements with coefficient of variation < 3.5% were recorded. Chromosome counting was performed on meristematic cells of roots obtained from germinated seeds or from hydroponic culture following the protocol of Jenkins and Hasterok (2007). Chromosome staining was performed with the DAPI fluorescent

marker (4', 6-diamino-2 phenylindole) and counting was done using a Motic BA410 fluorescence microscope. Ploidy levels were inferred from chromosome counts ($2n$) and GS estimations performed in the same accessions used in our transcriptome study and through contrasted GS and $2n$ values obtained in conspecific accessions that showed similar values (supplementary table S1). GS and chromosome values of the three annual *Brachypodium* species correspond to those indicated in Catalán et al. (2012).

Cytogenetic information retrieved from other authors is indicated in Table S2.

Experimental design, RNA isolation, library preparation and transcriptomic data of *Brachypodium*

In order to maximize the number of expressed transcripts we could sample, the individual plants were divided to produce four genetically identical plants and each plant received four treatments [control (water every 48 h, 25°C), soil drying stress (no water for one week), hot stress (40°C day/25°C night for 24 h), salt stress (500 mM NaCl in water, daily for two days)]. Total RNA was isolated from 50 – 200 mg of leaf tissue using the E.Z.N.A Plant RNA kit (Omega) or the RNeasy Plant Mini kit (Qiagen), following the manufacturers' protocols. RNA integrity, purity and concentration were respectively measured with Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer, NanoDrop, and Qubit, respectively. Pooled RNAs from the four treatments were used in subsequent RNA-Sequencing libraries. Library preparation was carried out by the Whitehead Genome Technology Core using TruSeq Stranded mRNA Library Prep Kit (Illumina, Inc.), generating Paired-End (PE) libraries with insert size of 300 to 600 bp. Library quantities were checked by Q-PCR and then sequenced using an Illumina HiSeq2500 platform at the Harvard University Bauer Core Facility.

Quality control of PE reads was performed with FastQC software (Andrews, 2010).

Adapters and low quality bases were removed and filtered with Trimmomatic-0.32

(Bolger *et al.*, 2014). Transcript sequences were assembled with trinityrnaseq-r20140717 (Grabherr *et al.*, 2011) using default parameters. *De novo* assembly of *Brachypodium* RNA-seq reads produced 72 to 160 thousand transcript isoforms with median lengths ranging between 414 to 555 bp (Tables S3ab).

Brachypodium RNA-seq data were deposited at ENA (European Nucleotide Archive; <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>) with run accession numbers ERR3633153 (*B. arbuscula*), ERR3634426 (*B. boissieri*), ERR3634464 (*B. hybridum*), ERR3634593 (*B. mexicanum*), ERR3634717 (*B. phoenicoides* Bpho422), ERR3634894 (*B. phoenicoides* Bpho6), ERR3634970 (*B. pinnatum*), ERR3636695 (*B. retusum*), ERR3636791 (*B. rupestre*) and ERR3636828 (*B. stacei*). *B. sylvaticum* RNA-seq data of the accession Brasy-Esp were obtained from the study by (Fox *et al.*, 2013). Transcriptomic data was also retrieved for the relatively close *Oryza sativa* (SRX738077) and *Hordeum vulgare* (ERR159679) outgroup species that were used to root the phylogenetic *Brachypodium* trees and to provide a stem branch for the grafting of ancestral homeologs/subgenomes.

Gene assembly for the orthology assessment

Raw Illumina reads from the resequenced *B. stacei* TE4.3 (NCBI SRR1802178) and *B. hybridum* BdTR6g (Phytozome) accessions were mapped to their respective *B. stacei* (ABR114; https://phytozome-next.jgi.doe.gov/info/Bstacei_v1_1) and *B. hybridum* (ABR113; https://phytozome-next.jgi.doe.gov/info/Bhybridum_v1_1) reference genomes with BWA v. 0.7.12-r1039 (Li and Durbin, 2009). Samtools v.1.13 was used to format, filter and sort the aligned sequences (quality mapped -q 60, sort and mpileup commands). Bcftools v.1.13 was executed to call the variants (call command), to normalize them and to remove duplicates lines (norm command), and to obtain consensus sequences (consensus command) (Li *et al.*, 2009; Li, 2011). In these processes heterozygous positions were substituted by missing data (N).

Phylogenomic and dating analyses of the *Brachypodium* and *Triticum-Aegilops* data sets

The alignments of the *Brachypodium* and *Triticum-Aegilops* data sets were conducted using GET_HOMOLOGUES-EST v09112017 (Contreras-Moreira *et al.*, 2017) and MAFFT v7.222 (Kato *et al.*, 2002; Kato and Standley, 2013), respectively. Maximum Likelihood analyses were performed with IQ-TREE v.1.6.1 (Minh *et al.*, 2013; Nguyen *et al.*, 2014; Chernomor *et al.*, 2016; Kalyaanamoorthy *et al.*, 2017). The best-fit evolutionary model of each data set was automatically selected by ModelFinder (Kalyaanamoorthy *et al.*, 2017) using the Akaike Information Criterion corrected (AICc). Topological congruence among alternative tree pairs was tested through Likelihood Ratio Test (SH-aLRT), and branch support ultrafast bootstrap searches were performed with 1000 replicates (Minh *et al.*, 2013; Chernomor *et al.*, 2016). The phylogenomic trees were conducted by “Partitioned analysis for multi-gene alignments” using the `-spp` option (Edge-proportional partition model with proportional branch lengths) of the IQ-TREE software.

In order to account for potential ILS in the selection of the most congruent diploid skeleton tree of each group, parallel analyses were conducted with the diploid sequences of the respective *Brachypodium* and *Triticum-Aegilops* data sets using ASTRAL v5.7.3 (Zhang *et al.*, 2018), and STAR and STEAC (R v.3.5.1 package; (Liu and Yu, 2010)) programs, which perform distance-based coalescence reconstructions.

Ancestral divergence ages of the *Brachypodium* homeologous subgenomes were estimated from a 322 nuclear core transcript data set (see Results) with BEAST 2.4.7 (Bouckaert *et al.*, 2014). We imposed the GTR substitution model, lognormal relaxed clock (clock rate = 1×10^{-4}) and Birth-Death tree models. We used two calibration points, imposing normal distribution secondary age constraints for the crown nodes of the BOP

clade [*Brachypodium* + *Oryza* + *Hordeum*] (normal prior mean = 51.7 Ma, SD = 1.9) and the *Brachypodium* + core pooids clade [*Brachypodium* + *Hordeum*] (normal prior mean = 33.2 Ma, SD = 9.5), following the grass-wide plastome based dating analysis of Sancho et al. (2018), and a broad uniform distribution prior for the uncorrelated lognormal distribution (uclid) mean (lower = 1×10^{-6} ; upper = 0.1) and an exponential prior for uclid standard deviation (SD). The convergence of the parameters was reached at 582×10^6 Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) generations in BEAST2 with a sampling frequency of 5×10^3 generations. The adequacy of parameters was checked using TRACER v.1.6 (<http://beast.bio.ed.ac.uk/Tracer>) with all the parameters showing Effective Sample Size (ESS) >200. Maximum clade credibility (MCC) trees were computed after discarding 10% of the respective saved trees as burn-in.

Performance of the ‘Subgenome Assignment’ algorithm in the hypothetical presence of incomplete lineage sorting (ILS) in *Brachypodium*

Theoretical probabilities of each tested case (Strategy 1: simulated grafted allopolyploid subgenomes on tree branches; Strategy 2: simulated allopolyploids that matched true allopolyploids) were estimated by COAL across the 10,395 topologies that could be computed with 7 tips. The performance of the subgenome assignment algorithm was tested through all ranges of probabilities in each of the two strategies. In Strategy 1 the highest probability corresponded always to the species tree branch in which the homeologous subgenome was grafted to by our *Subgenome Assignment* algorithm. In Strategy 2 the *Subgenome Assignment* algorithm recovered the expected placements of the mimic allopolyploid subgenomes, despite the different topological graftings. In our Strategy 1 we also tested the alternative distributions of *B. retusum* [A2 (c)+E1 (e)] and *B. rupestre* [E2 (e)+G (h)] to corroborate if contiguous topological graftings of a subgenome could affect the effectiveness of the algorithm. Despite some homeolog

grafting alternatives could be increased by ILS, as shown by these alternative tested distributions, they were discarded by the algorithm, indicating that grafting redundancies of the same subgenome in other close branches could be considered as artefacts.

References in Methods S1

Andrews, S. (2010) FastQC: a quality control tool for high throughput sequence data. , Available online at: <http://www.bioinformatics.bab>.

Bolger, A.M., Lohse, M. and Usadel, B. (2014) Trimmomatic: A flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics*, **30**, 2114–2120.

Bouckaert, R., Heled, J., Kühnert, D., Vaughan, T., Wu, C.-H., Xie, D., Suchard, M.A., Rambaut, A. and Drummond, A.J. (2014) BEAST 2: A Software Platform for Bayesian Evolutionary Analysis. *PLoS Comput. Biol.*, **10**, e1003537.

Catalán, P., López-Alvarez, D., Díaz-Pérez, A., Sancho, R. and López-Herranz, M.L. (2016) Phylogeny and Evolution of the Genus *Brachypodium*. In J. P. Vogel, ed. *Genetics and genomics of Brachypodium. Plant Genetics and Genomics: Crops Models*. Springer, pp. 9–38.

Catalán, P., Müller, J., Hasterok, R., et al. (2012) Evolution and taxonomic split of the model grass *Brachypodium distachyon*. *Ann. Bot.*, **109**, 385–405.

Chernomor, O., Haeseler, A. von and Minh, B.Q. (2016) Terrace Aware Data Structure for Phylogenomic Inference from Supermatrices. *Syst. Biol.*, **65**, 997–1008.

Contreras-Moreira, B., Cantalapiedra, C.P., García-Pereira, M.J., Gordon, S.P., Vogel, J.P., Igartua, E., Casas, A.M. and Vinuesa, P. (2017) Analysis of Plant Pan-Genomes and Transcriptomes with GET _ HOMOLOGUES-EST, a

Clustering Solution for Sequences of the Same Species. *Front. Genet.*, **8**, 1–16.

Díaz-Pérez, A., López-Alvarez, D., Sancho, R. and Catalán, P. (2018)

Reconstructing the origins and the biogeography of species' genomes in the highly reticulate allopolyploid-rich model grass genus *Brachypodium* using minimum evolution, coalescence and maximum likelihood approaches. *Mol. Phylogenet. Evol.*, **127**, 256–271.

Doležel, J., Greilhuber, J. and Suda, J. (2007) Estimation of nuclear DNA content in plants using flow cytometry. *Nat. Protoc.*, **2**, 2233–2244.

Fox, S.E., Preece, J., Kimbrel, J.A., Marchini, G.L., Sage, A., Cruzan, M.B. and Jaiswal, P. (2013) Sequencing and De Novo Transcriptome Assembly of *Brachypodium sylvaticum*. *Appl. Plant Sci.*, **1**, 1–8.

Grabherr, M.G., Haas, B.J., Yassour, M., et al. (2011) Trinity: reconstructing a full-length transcriptome without a genome from RNA-Seq data. *Nat. Biotechnol.*, **29**, 644–652.

Jenkins, G. and Hasterok, R. (2007) BAC “landing” on chromosomes of *Brachypodium distachyon* for comparative genome alignment. *Nat. Protoc.*, **2**, 88–98.

Kalyaanamoorthy, S., Minh, B.Q., Wong, T.K.F., Haeseler, A. von and Jermini, L.S. (2017) ModelFinder: fast model selection for accurate phylogenetic estimates. *Nat. Methods*, **14**, 587–589.

Katoh, K., Misawa, K., Kuma, K.I. and Miyata, T. (2002) MAFFT: A novel method for rapid multiple sequence alignment based on fast Fourier transform. *Nucleic Acids Res.*, **30**, 3059–3066.

Katoh, K. and Standley, D.M. (2013) MAFFT multiple sequence alignment software

- version 7: Improvements in performance and usability. *Mol. Biol. Evol.*, **30**, 772–780.
- Li, H.** (2011) A statistical framework for SNP calling, mutation discovery, association mapping and population genetical parameter estimation from sequencing data. *Bioinformatics*, **27**, 2987–2993.
- Li, H. and Durbin, R.** (2009) Fast and accurate short read alignment with Burrows-Wheeler transform. *Bioinformatics*, **25**, 1754–1760.
- Li, H., Handsaker, B., Wysoker, A., Fennell, T., Ruan, J., Homer, N., Marth, G., Abecasis, G. and Durbin, R.** (2009) The Sequence Alignment/Map format and SAMtools. *Bioinformatics*, **25**, 2078–2079.
- Liu, L. and Yu, L.** (2010) Phybase: An R package for species tree analysis. *Bioinformatics*, **26**, 962–963.
- Minh, B.Q., Nguyen, M.A.T. and Haeseler, A. von** (2013) Ultrafast Approximation for Phylogenetic Bootstrap. *Mol. Biol. Evol.*, **30**, 1188–1195.
- Nguyen, L.-T., Schmidt, H.A., Haeseler, A. von and Minh, B.Q.** (2014) IQ-TREE: A Fast and Effective Stochastic Algorithm for Estimating Maximum-Likelihood Phylogenies. *Mol. Biol. Evol.*, **32**, 268–274.
- Sancho, R., Cantalapiedra, C.P., López-Alvarez, D., Gordon, S.P., Vogel, J.P., Catalán, P. and Contreras-Moreira, B.** (2018) Comparative plastome genomics and phylogenomics of *Brachypodium*: Flowering time signatures, introgression and recombination in recently diverged ecotypes. *New Phytol.*, **218**, 1631–1644.
- Zhang, C., Rabiee, M., Sayyari, E. and Mirarab, S.** (2018) ASTRAL-III: Polynomial time species tree reconstruction from partially resolved gene trees. *BMC Bioinformatics*, **19**, 15–30.

